

Monolithic 16 GHz DBR mode-locked laser in an InP generic foundry platform: simulation and experiment

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Abstract

This paper presents a 16 GHz passive quantum well-based passive mode-locked laser (MLL) with an extended cavity, and Distributed Bragg reflectors (DBR) fabricated in the generic integration platform from Fraunhofer HHI. The performance of different operation regimes (Q-switching, mode-locking, and harmonic mode-locking) and pulse shape was studied for multiple lengths of the saturable absorber (SA). Characteristics for the gain and absorption spectra of the gain region and SA under various bias conditions were obtained from measurements of stand-alone devices and used to fit the analytical models applied in the simulations of the devices. The outcomes of these simulations of the MLL based on the Traveling Wave Equation and Transmission Line model are in good agreement with the measurements for the repetition rate and the behavior of different operation regimes.

Introduction

Semiconductor mode-locked lasers (MLLs) can produce a pulse at radio frequency (RF). They are used, for instance, in medical cutting, data communications, lidar, and metrology. Passive MLLs can be realized using linear or ring geometries [1]. They modulate the losses of the whole cavity by using a saturable absorber (SA) to synchronize the phase of the lasing modes. Inside the SA, the counterpropagating interaction of the light will cause a higher saturation by utilizing the colliding pulse mode-locking (CPM) configuration. Adding a passive component to a two-section linear MLL with cleaved facets acting as mirrors can improve its performance. First, it allows flexibility in selecting the total length of the cavity which defines the repetition rate. Second, it reduces self-phase modulation (SPM). Further improvements can be achieved by using the Multimode Interference Reflector (MIR) as a broadband reflector or the distributed Bragg reflector (DBR) as a narrow-band but wavelength-tunable reflector. Third, extending the cavity with an optical filter gives additional bandwidth control and can result in harmonic MLL operation. Finally, using other passive components enables the effective implementation of programmable photonics circuits [2].

In this paper, we theoretically and experimentally investigate the performance of operation regimes of a 16 GHz passive DBR mode-locked laser fabricated in the multi-project wafer (MPW) platform at Fraunhofer HHI. We further present optimization results of the SA length.

MLL operation regimes

The monolithic 16 GHz DBR mode-locked laser simulations have been performed using VPIcomponentMaker Photonics Circuits. We used the photonics transmission-line model (TLM) to simulate the behavior in the multi-quantum well (MQW) active region. The

Traveling-wave equations (TWE) were solved to obtain the electric field inside the active region.

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic diagram of the DBR mode-locked laser with an extended cavity: semiconductor optical amplifier (SOA); saturable absorber (SA); electrical isolation (ISO); Multi-mode interference coupler (MMI); distributed Bragg grating reflector (DBR); (b) Microscope image of the fabricated device; (c) Simulation results of different operation regimes: Q-switching (QS), mode-locking (ML), and harmonic mode-locking (HML); (d) measurement of different operation regimes.

Fig. 1(a) shows the schematic diagram of the fabricated 16 GHz DBR mode-locked laser. Fig. 1(b) shows the microscope image of the device under test (DUT). The MLL consists of a 900 μm SOA and a 50 μm reversely biased SA section separated by a 30 μm electrical isolation section (ISO). Two identical 300 μm distributed Bragg grating reflectors with 1550 nm center wavelength are used as mirrors. A 2x2 Multimode Interference coupler is used to transport the light out of the device. Deeply etched passive waveguides were included to extend the cavity. We investigated the mode-locking operation regimes by varying separately from each other the SOA current (50 mA to 300 mA) and the SA voltage (0 V to -2.6 V).

The carrier lifetime of the SA is dominated by the sweep-out time (τ) and is assumed to

Fig. 2. (a) Measurement and fitting curves of the SOA gain spectrum with carrier density from 1.7E24 to 2.59E24 $1/m^3$. (b) Measurement and fitting curve of the SA absorption spectrum under -4 V to 0 V.

follow a linear relationship with voltage in the logarithmic scale [3]. Fig. 2 shows the measured gain and absorption spectra of InGaAsP/InP SOAs with eight quantum wells for a range of injection currents and reverse biased voltage, as indicated above.

In the simulations, the following parabolic analytical model was used to fit the measured gain spectra:

$$g(f, N) = g_{peak}(N) \cdot \left\{ 1 - \left[\frac{f - f_{peak}(N)}{\Delta f(N)/2} \right]^2 \right\}$$

where g_{peak} is the gain peak of the spectra, N is the carrier density inside the TLM sections, f_{peak} is the gain peak frequency, and Δf is the gain bandwidth.

A Lorentzian analytical model was used to fit the absorption spectra of the SA:

$$\alpha_e(f, V_k) = \alpha_p(V_k) \cdot \frac{(\Delta f(V_k)/2)^2}{(f - f_p(V_k))^2 + (\Delta f(V_k)/2)^2}$$

where α is the absorption coefficient, f_p is the voltage-dependent absorption peak frequency, and Δf is the absorption bandwidth.

We determine the operation classification of the MLL based on the simulated pulse shape and measured electrical spectrum [4,5]. Fig. 1(c) shows simulation results of the different operation regimes of the MLL. At low V_{sa} (<0.4 V), the MLL worked in QS mode when the current was above the threshold and began lasing in the HML mode with the current increasing. As V_{sa} varies from 0.6 V to 0.8 V, which corresponds to τ varying from 25.11 ps to 15.84 ps, the carrier density of the SA cannot be reduced to zero in the ML mode, which means that the absorption ability of the SA is partially recovered within one round-trip time within the laser cavity. Consequently, this leads to a chirped pulse with a duration comparable to the round-trip time. In the HML mode, the net amplification is strong enough to support two pulses inside the cavity simultaneously. Because of the pulse duration time, the adjacent two pulses will overlap partially. When 0.8 V $< V_{sa} < 2.4$ V, τ ranges from 15.84 ps to 0.39 ps, and a wide and stable ML operation region was observed. When $\tau < 6.30$ ps, which corresponds to $V_{sa} < 1.2$ V, the carrier density inside the SA decreases to zero before the next pulse front enters the SA. With the increase of V_{sa} , the 3 dB bandwidth of the optical spectrum increases and results in narrower pulse generation.

The DUT was mounted on a temperature-controlled copper chuck and measured at 20 °C. A spot size converter (SSC) facilitated the coupling of the device to an optical fiber and reduced the coupling loss. We placed the SSC on the chip with a 7° tilt related to the chip edge to minimize the impact of back reflections from the interface to the laser cavity. The optical signal was detected using a THORLABS RXM40AF photoreceiver with 40 GHz bandwidth. The RF signal generated was recorded by a 50 GHz bandwidth electrical spectrum analyzer (ESA) Agilent 8565EC. Fig. 1(d) shows the different operation regimes derived from the experimental characterization of the MLL which are in good agreement with the simulations.

The MLL becomes unstable and operates between the ML and HML regimes for $V_{sa} < 0.8$ V. The highest fundamental RF peak of -10.66 dBm/res was found at $I_{soa} = 185$ mA and $V_{sa} = 1.4$ V. When $V_{sa} > 1.6$ V, the high starting lasing I_{soa} can be explained by the unexpected high loss inside the cavity.

Influence of SA length

We also studied the influence of the SA length L_{SA} on the operation regimes and pulse quality. Fig. 3(a, b, c) presents a simulation pulse train for various L_{SA} from 19 μ m to 90 μ m. All other parameters were kept the same as described in the previous section. A stable ML can be obtained for L_{SA} from 20 μ m to 80 μ m. When $L_{SA} < 20$ μ m, a stable HML can

be observed. The peak power has a positive correlation and the pulse duration time has a negative correlation with L_{SA} . The highest peak power (106.51 mW) and the sharpest full width at half maximum (FWHM) pulse duration (6.66 ps) can be observed at 19 μm .

Fig 3. (a, b, c) Simulated pulse train of SA length from 10 μm to 90 μm . (d) detected simulation peak power and FWHM of the pulse with different SA lengths. (all plots for $I_{\text{soa}} = 220 \text{ mA}$ and $V_{\text{sa}} = 2.0 \text{ V}$)

When $L_{SA} > 20 \mu\text{m}$, a stable ML pulse train can be observed. A jump in pulse width can be observed at the threshold of ML. After the threshold length, the highest peak power (183.40 mW) was obtained by 70 μm , and the sharpest FWHM (5.30 ps) can be observed at 80 μm . When $L_{SA} > 90 \mu\text{m}$, QS is observed, and the peak power significantly increases to 0.91 W. The average output peak power and FWHM as a function of L_{SA} are shown in Fig. 3(d).

Conclusion

We realized a 16 GHz MLL with a DBR reflector as an InP photonic integrated circuit. The operation condition at the passive mode-locking regime was theoretically and experimentally studied. Our simulations can qualitatively predict the different operation regimes of the MLL. For the ML region, we found the highest peak power of 183.4 mW at $L_{SA} = 70 \mu\text{m}$, and the sharpest pulse with FWHM = 5.3 ps at $L_{SA} = 80 \mu\text{m}$ by varying the length of the SA section.

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